

Five granular and 4 sprayable insecticides evaluated for yellow stem borer (YSB) control

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In 1982 and 1983, five granular and four spray insecticide formulations were tested against YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas*.

GR-11 seedlings were transplanted in 6-m² plots in a randomized block design with 6 replications. Granular insecticides were applied at 15 and 45 d after transplanting (DT); spray formulations were applied at 15, 45, and 60 DT. Deadhearts at 75 DT and whiteheads at harvest were counted; unhulled grain yield was recorded.

Of five granule and four spray formulations tested in three seasons,

cypermethrin spray was most effective (Table 1). Next was monocrotophos, followed by fenitrothion. Among granules, carbofuran was most effective; carbaryl + gamma BMC was least effective. Chlorpyrifos, phorate, and quinalphos were ineffective. None of the granule formulations were

effective during rainy season 1982.

Although cypermethrin spray resulted in the highest yield (3.43 t/ha), broadcasting carbofuran and spraying monocrotophos and fenitrothion significantly increased yield (2.94-3.01 t/ha) over the untreated control (Table 2). □

Table 2. Effect of granular and sprayable insecticide application on yield, Navsari, Gujarat, India, 1982 and 1983.

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		
		1982 rainy season	1983 summer	1983 rainy season
Carbofuran 3G	1.00	2.5 a	3.0 ab	3.4 b
Chlorpyrifos 10G	1.00	2.5 a	2.0 c	2.8 c
Phorate 10G	1.00	1.8 a	1.7 c	2.9 c
Quinalphos 5G	1.00	2.5 a	2.0 c	2.9 c
Carbaryl + gamma BHC 2+2G	1.00	2.6 a	2.1 bc	3.2 bc
Fenitrothion 50 EC	0.50	2.4 a	3.0 ab	3.4 b
Monocrotophos 36 EC	0.36	2.5 a	3.1 ab	3.4 b
Carbaryl 50 WP	1.00	2.2 a	2.1 bc	3.1 bc
Cypermethrin 25 EC	0.15	3.0 a	3.3 a	4.0 a
Untreated control	—	2.2 a	1.8 c	2.8 c

^aIn a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 1. Control of yellow stem borer by 5 granular and 4 sprayable insecticides. Navsari, Gujarat, India, 1982 and 1983.^a

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	1982 rainy season		1983 summer		1983 rainy season	
		Deadhearts (no.)	Whiteheads (no.)	Deadhearts (no.)	Whiteheads (no.)	Deadhearts (no.)	Whiteheads (no.)
Carbofuran 3G	1.00	8.7 cd	394.2 a	14.5 ab	139.8 a	18.5 ab	18.5 ab
Chlorpyrifos 10G	1.00	7.8 cd	304.8 a	21.5 c	187.7 c	26.5 de	40.8 cde
Phorate 10G	1.00	10.0 d	384.3 a	22.5 c	195.2 c	23.7 bcde	42.8 cde
Quinalphos 5G	1.00	9.7 d	340.7 a	18.5 c	185.8 c	23.5 bcde	41.5 cde
Carbaryl + gamma BHC 2 + 2G	1.00	9.5 d	348.0 a	14.5 ab	174.8 bc	19.7 abcd	36.7 bcd
Fenitrothion 50 EC	0.50	3.8 a	353.2 a	14.7 ab	148.0 ab	19.5 abc	24.8 abc
Monocrotophos 36 EC	0.36	6.3 bc	408.2 a	14.5 ab	124.7 a	19.0 abc	15.2 a
Carbaryl 50 WP	1.00	4.0 ab	337.5 a	17.8 c	186.3 c	21.8 bcd	44.3 de
Cypermethrin 25 EC	0.15	1.5 a	260.7 a	10.7 a	114.2 a	15.7 a	13.0 a
Untreated control	—	7.8 cd	370.8 a	23.0 c	199.0 c	29.0 e	58.9 e

^aNo. of deadhearts or whiteheads/6 m². In a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Daylength effect on development of 4 green leafhopper *Nephotettix* spp.

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Although diapause in the temperate species of rice green leafhopper (GLH) *N. cincticeps* (NC) has been well studied, not much is known about diapause in the tropical species *N. virescens* (NV), *N. nigropictus* (NN), and *N. malayanus* (NM). The three

tropical GLH species were subjected to the daylength and temperature conditions that induce diapause in NC.

Sixty newly hatched 1st instars of each species in individual test tubes (20 mm diameter and 170 mm long) were fed 5-d-old seedlings of the susceptible japonica variety Nipponbare. The insects were reared at 20°C under 8, 10, 12, 14, and 16 light hours (LH). The nymphs were fed fresh seedlings every 3 d and nymphal duration measured daily.

Short daylengths — 8, 10, and 12 LH — did not induce diapause in the

tropical species, although development was slightly prolonged as daylength shortened from 16 LH to 8 LH (see table). Nymphal development of both males and females of NN was significantly different in daylengths shorter than 10 LH and longer than 12 LH, except that for males under 8 LH development was about 1 d longer.

The development of NV males did not significantly differ between photoperiods, but that of females was significantly prolonged under photoperiods shorter than 12 LH. The 5-d difference between 8 LH and 16

LH was the largest among the tropical species of GLH. Under 16 LH, the development of both sexes of NM was significantly shorter than under other photoperiods.

Among the four species, only the temperate NC showed a clear lengthening of nymphal development under 10 LH. Under 8 LH, both the 4th- and the 5th-instar nymphs of NC exhibited arrested development; total development was prolonged to 74.2 d for males and 77.9 d for females. □

Developmental period of *Nephotettix* spp. exposed to different photoperiods at 20 °C. Japan.

Species		Developmental period ^a (d)				
		8 LH	10 LH	12 LH	14 LH	16 LH
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	Male	43.8 a	44.3 a	42.0 c	42.8 bc	42.3 c
	Female	46.3 a	46.4 a	44.1 b	44.4 b	44.0 b
<i>N. virescens</i>	Male	44.0 a	44.3 a	42.4 a	41.2 a	42.3 a
	Female	45.6 a	45.2 a	44.2 a	42.7 b	40.8 c
<i>N. cincticeps</i>	Male	74.2 a	55.2 b	44.0 c	39.6 d	40.4 d
	Female	77.9 a	58.6 b	43.7 c	42.8 c	42.9 c
<i>N. malayanus</i>	Male	44.1 a	43.8 a	43.6 a	42.7 a	40.3 b
	Female	46.7 a	46.1 a	45.3 a	45.3 a	43.4 b

^aIn a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

An earwig predator of Asian pink stem borer (PSB) in upland rice

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Asian PSB *Sesamia inferens* (Walker) can be particularly abundant in upland rice grown near sugarcane or related grasses. We found the earwig *Euborellia stali* (Dohrn) preying on PSB larva in stem borer-damaged tillers in upland ricefields in Claveria, northern Mindanao, Philippines. The predatory earwig bites the anal portion as the larva attempts to escape. There is a similar record of this earwig preying on the Oriental maize borer *Ostrinia furnacalis* (Guenée).

E. stali (see figure) has a shiny black body, light yellow brown legs with a black band on midfemora, and 17-segmented antennae with segments 14-15 colored white. It is common in dryland habitats and can be collected by digging in the soil at the base of rice hills.

The female earwig drags its prey out of the stem to her nest at the base of the plant to feed the newly hatched nymphs. A female shows maternal care to the 200-350 pale yellow and globular eggs it lays.

The nocturnal earwigs live 3-5 mo. Cage studies show that this earwig can consume 20-30 young PSB larvae a day. □

Adult of *E. stali* (a) and its feeding behavior on PSB larva inside the plant stem (b). Scale = 1 mm.

Ovicidal activity of eight insecticides against the rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino

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Two-wk-old potted rice plants were caged in nylon mesh. Field-collected male and female RWM adults were introduced into the cage and allowed to oviposit. Eggs on each potted plant were counted at 1 d. Plants with at least 10 eggs were used in the experiment.

Four potted plants laden with 2-d-old RWM eggs were placed in a mylar cage and sprayed with 25 ml (equivalent to spray water volume of

Ovicidal activity of 8 insecticides applied as foliar spray on plants with 2-d-old eggs of RWM. IRRI, 1986.

Insecticide	Formulation	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Egg mortality ^a (%)
Deltamethrin	2.5 EC	0.012	98 a
Triazophos	40 EC	0.4	97 a
Azinphos-ethyl	40 EC	0.4	94 a
BPMC	50 EC	0.4	50 b
Carbaryl	85 WP	0.4	42 b
Carbosulfan	20 EC	0.4	39 b
Buprofezin	25 WP	0.125	32 b
Malathion	51 EC	0.4	25 b

^aAv of replications. All means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Abbott's formula was applied for corrected percent egg mortality.

1,000 liters/ ha) of each test insecticide using a 1-liter plastic hand sprayer.

Deltamethrin, triazophos, and azinphos-ethyl were highly ovicidal

(see table). Some ovicidal activity occurred with BPMC, carbaryl, carbosulfan, buprofezin, and malathion. □